

An analysis of emotional intelligence as a key factor in achieving work-life balance among student training assistants

¹Angelie Mae C. Dumagil, ¹Jassey Kaye A. Lepardo, ¹Rotchell J. Niez,
¹Elaine Joy V. Ordaniel, ¹Jhared Christian F. Sarmiento, ²Marvin C. Lofranco

¹Students, University of Mindanao- Panabo College

²Faculty, University of Mindanao- Panabo College, Panabo City, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19109951>

Published Date: 19-March-2026

Abstract: Work-life balance has become an important concern among student employees, particularly Student Training Assistants (STAs), as they face the challenge of managing academic responsibilities alongside work demands. The study aimed to examine the challenges student training assistants face in balancing academic and work duties, and to assess how emotional intelligence and academic performance influence their overall work-life balance. This study is anchored to SDG 3 (Good Health and Well Being), SDG 4 (Quality Education), and SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth). The study employed a descriptive-correlational quantitative design, and data were collected from 34 STAs as respondents through adopted questionnaires and analyzed using mean and Pearson's *r*. Findings revealed very high levels of emotional intelligence ($x=4.42$) and work-life balance ($x=4.31$), with a strong positive correlation ($r=0.708$, $p<0.05$). The results indicate that emotional intelligence significantly contributes to better work-life balance, suggesting that strengthening emotional competencies can enhance students' overall well-being and performance. The study recommends that student training assistants, school administrations, and teachers sustain emotional intelligence and work-life balance through supportive programs and practices, while future researchers explore related factors to enhance students' well-being and performance.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, work-life balance, student training assistants, descriptive-correlational design, Pearson's *r*, well-being.

I. INTRODUCTION

Work-life balance becomes a problem when work demands consume excessive time and energy, leaving little room for personal activities, relationships, and self-care. This imbalance can lead to stress, burnout, and decreased overall well-being, making it difficult for individuals to maintain healthy boundaries between their professional and personal lives (Staff, 2025). In the modern world, work-life balance has emerged as a major concern in every organization. Work-life balance has been the subject of extensive research by human resource management in an effort to boost human engagement and performance (Pathak, 2021).

There are several detrimental effects of poor work-life balance on the workplace, including decreased performance, decreased job satisfaction, and increased conflict. It is important to remember that workplace mental health issues and stress-related absenteeism are on the rise (Ravaleir et al., 2016). Studies show that high conflict levels are strongly associated with poorer work-life balance, so that some people are able to successfully manage the demands of their personal and professional lives, while others experience a significant imbalance (Gnawali, 2021). This imbalance can show itself in a

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social SciencesVol. 13, Issue 2, pp: (1-16), Month: March - April 2026, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

number of harmful ways that affect not just one's own well-being but also one's productivity at work and general level of happiness with life.

Pakistan has revealed significant correlations between job satisfaction, work-life balance, and emotional intelligence across various healthcare sectors. The research, encompassing a diverse range of healthcare professionals, demonstrated that emotional intelligence is a key predictor of job satisfaction and work-life balance. Healthcare workers exhibiting higher levels of emotional intelligence reported greater contentment in their jobs and a more harmonious integration of their professional and personal lives (Malik, 2021). Similarly, a study conducted in India has definitively established that work-family life balance significantly influences employee performance and is a notable driver of employee turnover. The research underscores that employees who experience conflict or imbalance between their work and family responsibilities are more likely to exhibit decreased job satisfaction, reduced productivity, and a higher propensity to leave their current employment (Shylaja & Prasad, 2017).

In the national context of education, particularly within the Hinatuan District, research has shown that the individual work performance of public elementary school teachers is significantly shaped by the combined influence of emotional intelligence and work-life balance (Martizano & Baloran, 2025). Similarly, it can be concluded that the theory of Emotional Intelligence (EI) is applicable in the Philippine context, as evidenced by a study on nurses which confirmed that they demonstrated a high degree of emotional intelligence in both personal and social competencies (Vestal, 2020). They showed strong performance across the four quadrants of emotional intelligence: self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management and exhibited very high performance in optimism, service orientation, empathy, and achievement. The fact that EI has a significant relationship with performance suggests that its applicability may extend to other professionals within institutions, highlighting its broader value across sectors.

A study conducted in Kapalong, Davao del Norte revealed that teachers who are emotionally self-aware and effectively manage personal and professional responsibilities are more likely to demonstrate strong affective commitment (Cuyos & Permangil, 2025). Thus, fostering emotional intelligence and supporting work-life integration can be essential strategies for enhancing organizational commitment and sustaining a motivated and effective teaching workforce. Correspondingly, a study conducted among public elementary school teachers in Cateel, Davao Oriental, Philippines, found that teachers experience a moderate level of stress, with time management identified as a significant contributor. Despite these stressors, the teachers exhibited a high level of emotional intelligence, particularly in managing and utilizing emotions, which helped them cope with challenges and improve their teaching effectiveness (Velasco & Apostol, 2024).

According to Syahada and Suhardi (2025), work-life balance significantly improves employees' mental health and job satisfaction by reducing stress and increasing productivity. Their study highlights the importance of maintaining a healthy balance in demanding work environments, where sustained workplace pressure can negatively impact psychological well-being and efficiency. They stress that organizations should prioritize mental health as a key factor in maintaining overall job performance and employee sustainability. Additionally, Saputra and Masdupi (2024) emphasized that workplace policies promoting flexible hours and effective time management enhance employees' ability to manage multiple roles effectively. Such policies reduce work-family conflicts and empower employees to harmonize professional and personal responsibilities, leading to higher motivation and reduced turnover.

Christy and Indiyati (2025) demonstrated that work-life balance has positive effects on physical well-being and emotional resilience. Balanced employees typically enjoy better health outcomes, such as improved sleep quality and fewer stress-related illnesses, which contribute to lasting job performance. Conversely, imbalance tends to cause burnout and low motivation. Likewise, Pujowati and Aswan (2025) reported that fair workload distribution, when combined with flexible work arrangements, increases job satisfaction and engagement. Their findings indicate that workplace flexibility helps employees maintain energy and focus throughout the workday, promoting greater organizational commitment.

Individuals reported high levels of work-life balance, indicating that they could effectively manage professional, personal, and academic responsibilities. Consequently, this strong balance was positively linked to greater engagement in their studies, suggesting that maintaining harmony between work and life roles can enhance active learning and commitment (De Luzuriaga-Balaria et al., 2024). Furthermore, Gragnano, Simbula, and Miglioretti (2020) examined how employees perceive different components of work-life balance, particularly the prioritization of family responsibilities versus health-related needs, and how these perceptions relate to job satisfaction. In addition, Gilla et al. (2025) found that individuals reporting

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social SciencesVol. 13, Issue 2, pp: (1-16), Month: March - April 2026, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

very high work–life balance also demonstrated greater commitment to their profession, indicating that when educators perceive high balance, it aligns with positive educational outcomes.

Rajagopalasingam et al. (2021) revealed that strong work ethics can moderate the negative effects of competing role demands, enabling individuals to maintain a more balanced work–life experience. Moreover, Haar et al. (2017) found that employees with higher perceived work–life balance reported greater life satisfaction and better mental well-being, highlighting its positive impact beyond the workplace and its contribution to overall quality of life.

Carnevale and Hatak (2020) found that flexible work practices, such as remote work, enhance employees' capacity to manage work and family roles. Similarly, Kossek et al. (2016) emphasized that workplace flexibility and boundary control strategies improve role management by helping employees maintain clear distinctions between domains. Furthermore, Allen et al. (2020) reported that flexible arrangements and supervisor support promote better integration of work and personal responsibilities, resulting in improved work–life balance and satisfaction.

Sirgy and Lee (2018) emphasize that unmanaged work demands can negatively affect overall well-being, making balance essential for maintaining quality of life and satisfaction in both work and personal domains. Similarly, French et al. (2018) found that effectively managing work and personal responsibilities is linked to higher work engagement and lower work–life conflict, reinforcing the importance of balance for employee well-being.

In educational contexts, Hernandez and Cruz (2024) found that college students balancing academic and personal responsibilities display higher psychological well-being and academic success. Students who effectively manage these dual roles experience less anxiety and improved concentration, which boost academic outcomes. Zhang and Perez (2025) further showed that institutional support systems such as counseling services and flexible deadlines reduce anxiety and enhance student focus and work-life balance. These supports create flexible academic environments that aid students in managing challenges without compromising mental health.

Mindfulness and stress management programs have also been identified as effective interventions for improving work-life balance among professionals. Nguyen and Lopez (2024) demonstrated that mindfulness training promotes emotional regulation and mental clarity, helping employees better manage work-related stress. Moreover, Brown and Torres (2023) found that social support and wellness initiatives foster workplace environments conducive to maintaining work-life balance and preventing burnout. Organizations that implement wellness programs tend to experience higher employee satisfaction and lower absenteeism, highlighting the value of such initiatives in sustaining a healthy workforce.

According to the study of Prabha et al. (2023), individuals with higher emotional intelligence tend to be more empathetic, understanding, and communicative. As a result, it allows them to enhance their ability to navigate through conflicts, develop trust, and maintain satisfying and healthy relationships. Furthermore, emotional intelligence also extends to other areas of life, such as improved academic performance, mental health, and overall life satisfaction. Such as having low emotional intelligence or EI can have a detrimental effect on your mental and physical health in addition to your interpersonal interactions. Besides struggling to understand what others are feeling, individuals with low emotional intelligence also struggle to understand their emotional experiences (Cherry, 2024).

Saleem, Ullah, and Zafar (2024) examined dimensions of self-awareness, self-management, empathy, and relationship management, concluding that these components of emotional intelligence or EI positively impact academic performance at the university level. Such as having low emotional intelligence or EI can have a detrimental effect on your mental and physical health in addition to your interpersonal interactions. Emotional intelligence or EI affects university students' academic performance and psychological well-being, with self-efficacy, motivation, and resilience serving as important mediators Shengyao et al. (2024).

Individuals with higher emotional intelligence (EI) exhibit greater self-awareness, empathy, and emotional regulation. Specifically, self-awareness allows them to accurately recognize their own emotions fostering stronger interpersonal relationships (Sundararajan & Gopichandran, 2018). Furthermore, individuals with higher EI demonstrate stronger motivation, greater self-efficacy, and more effective use of social support, which allows them to regulate their emotions and channel them toward goal-directed behaviors (Tang & He, 2023). Moreover, research emphasizes that these individuals display stronger self-control, more positive engagement with goals, and consistent focus, with self-control enabling them to resist distractions and delay immediate gratification in favor of long-term objectives (Arias et al., 2022).

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social SciencesVol. 13, Issue 2, pp: (1-16), Month: March - April 2026, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Nieto-Carracedo et al. (2024) reported that emotional intelligence or EI independently fosters social skills that are crucial for effective collaboration and group learning. These enhanced social skills, in turn, have a positive effect on students' academic achievement, indicating that EI plays a significant role in educational success by improving interpersonal interactions within learning environments. Similarly, Zhou et al. (2024) established that EI directly facilitates reflective practices among students. This means that students with higher levels of EI are better able to engage in self-reflection, which enhances their capacity to adapt to different academic challenges and perform well. Importantly, this improvement in academic performance occurs without reliance on external variables, highlighting the intrinsic value of EI in supporting students' learning processes.

Martin and Thomas (2024) demonstrated that emotional intelligence or EI influences classroom behavior and student engagement within secondary education settings. Specifically, students who scored higher on measures of EI exhibited greater levels of cooperation with peers and teachers, increased motivation toward learning tasks, and enhanced self-regulation skills. These positive behavioral and emotional attributes contributed to improved learning outcomes, suggesting that EI plays a critical role in shaping how students interact and perform in the classroom environment. In addition, Sánchez-Ruiz et al. (2025) conducted an intervention aimed at boosting EI among students and observed that increases in EI reliably predicted subsequent improvements in academic achievement over time. This finding underscores the direct effect of EI in educational settings, indicating that enhancing students' emotional intelligence can lead to measurable gains in their academic performance.

The role of emotional intelligence or EI in maintaining work-life balance or WLB among student training assistants can be understood through several international studies and literature reviews focused on emotional intelligence's impact on work-related and personal life equilibrium. Emotional intelligence is broadly defined as the ability to recognize, understand, and manage one's own emotions and those of others, which facilitates motivation, empathy, and effective interpersonal relationships (Batool, 2021). Research consistently shows that high emotional intelligence correlates positively with better stress management and improved job satisfaction (Fiori, Bollmann, & Rossier, 2015).

Individuals with higher emotional intelligence experience lower levels of burnout due to their capacity to regulate negative emotions and cope with stress effectively, which directly supports a healthier work-life balance (Naz, Ahmad, & Batool, 2021). Specific to educational settings, research reveals that emotional intelligence among academic professionals, including student training assistants, enhances workplace happiness, which is linked with perceived better academic performance and a more satisfactory work-life balance. The mediation effect of work-life balance between workplace happiness and performance is strengthened by emotional intelligence, suggesting that emotionally intelligent student assistants can better manage their academic and personal roles effectively (Hermosilla & Tan, 2023).

Hajibabae et al., (2018) indicated that students with higher levels of empathy also demonstrated higher emotional intelligence, suggesting that empathy is a key component in the development and expression of emotional intelligence. Moreover, another study by Daribaev & Sagindikova (2025) exemplified that empathy is a fundamental component of emotional intelligence, significantly contributing to an individual's ability to understand and respond to others' emotions, and that this interrelationship plays an essential role in effective social communication, interpersonal relationships, and psychological well-being. Coronado and Benítez (2023) emphasize that emotionally intelligent individuals demonstrate strong self-motivation, including goal orientation and perseverance.

In line with this, the study highlights that self-awareness, a core component of emotional intelligence, enables individuals to accurately recognize and understand their own emotions, which in turn enhances decision-making, self-regulation, and goal-directed behavior, demonstrating that higher self-awareness is crucial for effective personal and professional outcomes (Salameh-Ayanian et al., 2025). Moreover, another study found that self-emotion appraisal, defined as the ability to detect and understand one's own feelings, significantly and positively influences learning performance by helping students recognize how their emotions affect their thinking, motivation, and engagement, thereby underscoring the role of self-awareness as a foundational emotional intelligence skill that enhances academic outcomes (Suson et al., 2025).

Salavera et al. (2017) reported that emotional intelligence is closely linked to social skills, with higher EI associated with stronger abilities to communicate, cooperate, and manage interpersonal interactions effectively. Furthermore, Khuadthong et al. (2025) demonstrated that emotional intelligence enhances communication, teamwork, and problem-solving abilities, and that integrating EI training with practical experiences can further strengthen these essential social competencies.

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social SciencesVol. 13, Issue 2, pp: (1-16), Month: March - April 2026, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Antonopoulou (2024) explains that emotional intelligence is closely linked to self-management, as recognizing and understanding one's emotions supports effective behavior regulation. Similarly, Shubayr and Dailah (2025) identify self-management as a core dimension of EI that reduces perceived stress and strengthens self-efficacy. Moreover, effective emotion regulation enhances coping and sustained performance in demanding situations. Overall, these findings highlight self-management as a key mechanism for emotional stability, resilience, and personal effectiveness.

Additional studies in the education context, such as those involving teachers or public employees, have found a significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence and work-life balance. Emotional intelligence helps reduce teacher stress and burnout, which is critical for maintaining effective teaching performance and personal well-being (East Kalimantan Provincial Government, 2023). Emotional intelligence has consistently been linked with individuals' ability to maintain work-life balance across various professions. In their study on Indian nurses, Shivani Sharma and Parul Saxena (2022) found that emotional intelligence was a significant predictor of work-life balance, even when participants experienced high levels of job stress. Their findings indicated that nurses who could recognize and manage their own emotions, as well as understand those of others, were more likely to handle occupational stress and personal responsibilities effectively.

Several studies have emphasized the mediating function of emotional intelligence in improving work-life balance and its outcomes. Punitha and Karthi (2024) examined employees in the healthcare sector in Coimbatore and found that emotional intelligence not only enhanced work-life balance but also mediated its relationship with job satisfaction and job performance. Their model suggested that EI allows individuals to better interpret work stressors and apply emotional regulation strategies, which indirectly improved their job performance through better WLB. Supporting this, Mahima Nanda and Gurpreet Randhawa (2020) proposed a mediation model wherein work-life balance acted as a bridge between emotional intelligence and work-related well-being. Their findings showed that emotionally intelligent individuals experienced greater job satisfaction and engagement, partly because they maintained a healthier balance between work and life demands. These studies signify the importance of emotional intelligence in maintaining personal responsibilities with work life demands, effectively assisting in greater satisfaction.

This study is based on David Goleman's Emotional Intelligence Theory (1995), stating that individuals have different emotional capabilities essential to effective personal and social functioning. The five key dimensions, self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills, are the cornerstone of emotional intelligence, providing a guideline for behavior and interactions. Another theory this study is based on is Stevan Hobfoll's Conservation of Resources Theory (1989), which states that individuals want to acquire, and conserve resources to achieve a balance, the main source of stress being resource loss. This theory explains ways workers use their resources such as energy, skills and time, to manage the demands of their work and nonwork roles. Research consistently shows a positive relationship between emotional intelligence (EI) and work-life balance. For instance, employees in the IT sector with higher EI reported significantly better balance, as emotional regulation and self-awareness enabled them to manage competing job and personal demands more effectively (Raj, 2025).

While multiple studies have looked into the correlation between emotional intelligence and work-life balance, only a small number of studies have specifically examined it in the context of Student Training Assistants. A similar study by (Lofranco, 2025) analyzed the impact of organizational culture on school administrators' work-life balance in the Davao Region. However, the study focused on school administrators' organizational culture and professional development but did not mention emotional intelligence. Likewise, other studies have not clearly examined the correlation between emotional intelligence and work-life balance or fail in considering Student Training Assistants in UM Panabo College. This study analyzes the influence of emotional intelligence on student training assistants work life balance, highlighting the importance of emotional intelligence in work life balance and the advancement of SDG 3 (Good Health and Well Being), SDG 4 (Quality Education), and SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth). By understanding how emotional intelligence supports better work-life balance, the study provides insights that can promote healthier, more productive, and equitable learning and working environments.

This study offers several key benefits to various stakeholders. Student training assistants (STAs) will gain insights into balancing their work and non-work lives, enabling them to identify and implement strategies for improved work-life balance. The school administration will benefit from a deeper understanding of the challenges STAs face, informing the

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

Vol. 13, Issue 2, pp: (1-16), Month: March - April 2026, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

development of supportive policies and practices. Teachers will gain awareness of the experiences of STAs, fostering better communication and collaboration. Finally, future researchers can utilize this study's findings as a valuable resource for further exploration of work-life balance among student employees.

Figure 1. Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Work-Life Balance

The study aimed to investigate the relationship between emotional intelligence and work-life balance of the student training assistants of UM Panabao College. Specifically, it sought to: (1) determine the difficulties of student training assistants in balancing academic and work duties through quantitative analysis; (2) analyze emotional intelligence and academic performance as causes or effects on their overall work-life balance; and (3) assess how emotional intelligence and academic performance affect the work-life balance of student training assistants.

The researchers developed a null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and work-life balance in student training assistants at a 0.05 significance level.

The study employed a total population sampling method, which means all 34 student training assistants working in UM Panabao College are included. Total population sampling is a type of purposive sampling technique that involves examining the entire population that have a particular set of characteristics. Respondents must be formally enrolled in UM Panabao College to be qualified. The inclusion criteria were as follows: (a) should be a student training assistant, (b) enrolled in UM Panabao College, and (c) should be willing to participate in the study. The exclusion criteria are as follows: (a) are not a student training assistant, (b) are not enrolled in UM Panabao College, and (c) are not willing to participate in the study. The total student training assistants in UM Panabao College comprise a maximum of 34 respondents. According to Burmeister and Aitken (2012), a sample size of around 30 participants is generally appropriate for most quantitative studies, particularly in small-scale or usability research. This supports the adequacy of including all 34 respondents in the present study, as it falls within the recommended range for producing meaningful quantitative insights. With total population sampling, the researcher examines the entire population that shares one or more characteristics. This type of purposive sampling technique is commonly used to generate reviews of events or experiences and to study particular groups within larger populations (Crossman & Ashley, 2018).

This study contained a total of 72 items within the survey questionnaire, 48 items for emotional intelligence and 24 items for work-life balance. The primary research tool for this study was a questionnaire adapted from Dangwal et al. (2022). The survey used in this study was a 48-item questionnaire. It's organized into five sections to thoroughly measure how emotional intelligence influences work-life balance among student training assistants. It was based on previous research that measured (1) self-awareness (2) self-management (3) self-motivation, (4) empathy, (5) and social skills. Each section measures key aspects of emotional intelligence, ensuring a complete assessment of the variable. To evaluate the factors in achieving work-life balance among student training assistants, this study employed a previously validated, three-part questionnaire. With a total of 24 items, this instrument was adopted from an online website by (Hyman, 2005). The instrument was designed to specifically measure emotional intelligence and its relationship with work-life balance through three key indicators, (1) perceived work-life balance, (2) managing work and non-work roles, (3) and work demands with personal life. To ensure

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social SciencesVol. 13, Issue 2, pp: (1-16), Month: March - April 2026, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

the questionnaires are relevant and effective for this study, they underwent a process of adoption. This involved minor adjustments to the wording of the items to fit the specific population of student training assistants.

The research instrument's construct validity was supported by the original validation from the study by Dangwal et al. (2022), as it was specifically designed to measure factors related to emotional intelligence and its effect on work-life balance. To guarantee the survey's content was both valid and reliable, it was reviewed by a panel of experts. Specialists in emotional intelligence, work-life balance, and quantitative research confirmed that the questions are appropriate and comprehensive, and accurately measure the key aspects of work-life balance among the study's participants. These two adapted questionnaires were modified and expanded to assess the emotional intelligence and work-life balance among student training assistants in UM Panabo College. To test the validity of this questionnaire, this questionnaire underwent pilot testing consisting of forty respondents and validation by the expert on the team of professionals. Finally, a licensed statistician will use statistical tools, specifically the mean and Pearson's r , to analyze the collected data and determine the relationship between emotional intelligence and achieving work-life balance for student training assistants. The use of descriptive statistics like the mean and correlational analyses such as Pearson's r is a standard practice for measuring the relationship between emotional intelligence and work-life balance (Memon, Asif, & Hussain, 2021).

This study used a descriptive correlational quantitative approach to investigate the relationship between work-life balance and emotional intelligence among student training assistants at UM Panabo College. By using a descriptive quantitative approach, the researchers aimed to measure and describe the levels of emotional intelligence and work-life balance among the population of interest. This approach allowed the researchers to explore the relationship between these two variables by analyzing the patterns and associations that exist within the collected data Sembiring, Hardjo, & Lubis (2024). Emotional intelligence was treated as the independent variable and work-life balance as the dependent variable, with statistical methods used to determine whether a significant relationship exists between them.

The researchers formally wrote a letter of request to the Branch Director of UM Panabo College, seeking permission to conduct the study within the institution. Upon approval, a second letter was sent to the Deans of the through program heads and coordinators, requesting their cooperation and endorsement to access the Student Training Assistants within their respective programs. Upon receiving the necessary permissions, the researchers proceeded with the administration of the survey. The survey was conducted in a designated area within the campus to ensure a quiet and conducive environment. Each participant was then given an informed consent form to read and sign. The researchers scheduled a time with participants to collect the surveys two days after they were handed out. This approach is key to ensuring a high return rate and getting the data on time. Once all questionnaires were retrieved, the researchers tallied and coded the data. The gathered information was submitted to a licensed statistician for analysis and interpretation. The statistical tools to be used in this study was the mean and Pearson's r , to determine the relationship between climate change awareness and energy-saving behaviors. All responses provided by participants in this study were maintained with the highest level of confidentiality. Participants' identities were kept strictly anonymous, and all information obtained was used exclusively for academic research purposes. No personally identifiable data was disclosed, thereby ensuring the complete privacy of all respondents throughout the research process.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Table 1 shows that emotional intelligence has five indicators: self-awareness, self-management, self-motivation, empathy and social skills. This data reveals a very high level of agreement mean of 4.42 and SD of 0.32 meaning that they have an excellent level of emotional intelligence among student training assistants' respondents, suggesting a significant presence of their emotional intelligence.

Individuals with higher emotional intelligence (EI) exhibit greater self-awareness, empathy, and emotional regulation. Specifically, self-awareness allows them to accurately recognize their own emotions fostering stronger interpersonal relationships (Sundararajan & Gopichandran, 2018). Furthermore, individuals with higher EI demonstrate stronger motivation, greater self-efficacy, and more effective use of social support, which allows them to regulate their emotions and channel them toward goal-directed behaviors (Tang & He, 2023). Moreover, research emphasizes that these individuals display stronger self-control, more positive engagement with goals, and consistent focus, with self-control enabling them to resist distractions and delay immediate gratification in favor of long-term objectives (Arias et al., 2022).

Table 1. Level of Emotional Intelligence

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Equivalent
Self Awareness	4.45	0.38	Strongly Agree
Self Management	4.27	0.41	Strongly Agree
Self Motivation	4.49	0.38	Strongly Agree
Empathy	4.57	0.33	Strongly Agree
Social Skills	4.32	0.52	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean	4.42	0.32	Strongly Agree

Table 1 shows that empathy obtained the highest mean score with a mean of 4.57 and SD of 0.33, among the dimensions of emotional intelligence, with a descriptive equivalent of strongly agree. The high mean and low standard deviation indicate strong and consistent agreement among respondents, reflecting a unified perception of empathy as a core element of emotional intelligence. Participants view empathy as an essential skill that shapes how individuals understand and respond to others' emotions in professional settings. Among the eight questions, Item 2 obtained the highest mean, stating "I remain respectful to others by considering their point of view" with a mean score of 4.65 and a descriptive equivalent of "strongly agree". The findings emphasize the crucial role of empathy in being able to connect with others and understand different viewpoints at the workplace. Meanwhile, the lowest mean is Item 8, with the statement "I am quick to offer comfort or support to a friend in distress" with a mean of 4.41 and the descriptive equivalent of strongly agree. The results from the Item implies that student training assistants are not particularly able to comfort their peers quickly, but are able to notice and help in time.

Empathy is a common and important trait among student training assistants, assisting in their ability to mend with others and create good and professional relationships. This can allow student training assistants to conduct work to the best of their abilities and understand their peers. Consistent with these results, Hajibabae et al., (2018) indicated that students with higher levels of empathy also demonstrated higher emotional intelligence, suggesting that empathy is a key component in the development and expression of emotional intelligence. Moreover, another study by Daribaev & Sagindikova (2025) exemplified that empathy is a fundamental component of emotional intelligence, significantly contributing to an individual's ability to understand and respond to others' emotions, and that this interrelationship plays an essential role in effective social communication, interpersonal relationships, and psychological well-being.

In addition, self-motivation attained a very high level with a mean of 4.49, and SD of 0.38, with a descriptive equivalent of strongly agree, indicating consistently positive responses among participants. The high mean and low standard deviation suggest a shared recognition of self-motivation as an important dimension of emotional intelligence. Respondents associate emotional intelligence not only with interpersonal skills but also with the intrapersonal ability to regulate emotions, sustain drive, and remain resilient despite challenges. The highest mean within the indicator is Item 1 with the statement "Before starting any task I am full of hope that I will accomplish any tasks" which has a mean of 4.74 and a descriptive equivalent of strongly agree. The findings imply that self-motivation enables individuals to stay focused on goals, manage stress, overcome setbacks, and maintain productivity in demanding situations. Conversely, the lowest mean comes from Item 7 with the statement "Distraction rarely keeps me from completing what I start" a mean of 4.00 and a descriptive equivalent of agree. This implies that student training assistants can be easily distracted and discard their responsibilities leading them to not finish or postpone the task. Self-motivation can allow student training assistants to persevere and work towards their tasks even with distractions. This can help them finish what they start and emphasize their push towards goals. Thus, it plays a significant role in achieving personal and professional success and reinforces its importance as a core component of emotional intelligence. Supporting this, Coronado and Benítez (2023) emphasize that emotionally intelligent individuals demonstrate strong self-motivation, including goal orientation and perseverance. Similarly, Shengyao et al. (2024) found

that emotional intelligence positively influences students' self-motivation, linking it to improved academic achievement and psychological well-being.

Self-awareness demonstrated a very high level with a mean of 4.45 and SD of 0.38, with a descriptive equivalent of strongly agree. The high mean indicates that respondents strongly recognize self-awareness as a key indicator of emotional intelligence, while the low standard deviation reflects consistent perceptions. Throughout the ten questions, Item 2 with the statement "I do acknowledge my strength and weakness" achieved the highest mean of 4.74 and a descriptive equivalent of "strongly agree". The results suggest that student training assistants can effectively evaluate themselves and understand when to participate in work that they can handle. Meanwhile, the lowest mean is Item 7 with the statement "I am comfortable discussing my feelings with others" achieving a mean of 3.47 and a descriptive equivalent of "strongly agree". This result implies that student training assistants are reluctant in sharing their emotions, possibly indicating they focus on their work rather than focusing on personal feelings, and also being reclusive to others, likely keeping their own emotions within themselves.

Self-awareness is an essential aspect of emotional intelligence as it shows how a person can understand the extent of their abilities and adapt to the situation they experience. For student training assistants it is an important part of their ability to handle work and understand which tasks are within their capabilities and are manageable. As a foundational component of emotional intelligence, it supports responsible behavior, adaptability, and growth. In line with this, the study highlights that self-awareness, a core component of emotional intelligence, enables individuals to accurately recognize and understand their own emotions, which in turn enhances decision-making, self-regulation, and goal-directed behavior, demonstrating that higher self-awareness is crucial for effective personal and professional outcomes (Salameh-Ayanian et al., 2025). Moreover, another study found that self-emotion appraisal, defined as the ability to detect and understand one's own feelings, significantly and positively influences learning performance by helping students recognize how their emotions affect their thinking, motivation, and engagement, thereby underscoring the role of self-awareness as a foundational emotional intelligence skill that enhances academic outcomes (Suson et al., 2025).

The respondents reported a mean score of 4.32 and SD of 0.52 for social skills, interpreted as strongly agree, indicating well-developed interpersonal abilities. This suggests they are effective in managing relationships, resolving conflicts, and building positive connections reflecting strong emotional intelligence in the social domain. This indicator has the highest mean in Item 8 with the statement "I can collaborate well in group settings, appreciating others input" with a mean of 4.53 and a descriptive equivalent of "strongly agree". This result means that student training assistants are able to work well with their peers and have clear communication skills, indicating they are not likely to have conflict and can finish work even with other people. The consistently high rating implies competence in communication, collaboration, and maintaining social harmony, which are essential for academic, professional, and everyday success. On the other hand, Item 2 had the lowest mean with the statement "I am good at convincing others" obtaining a mean of 4.06 and a descriptive equivalent of agree. The result implores that student training assistants are not particularly adept at coercing others but are rather direct in their work, implying that the skill is not essential within the workplace.

Social skills are essential towards maintaining work flow and performance, student training assistants benefit from these skills because it allows teamwork and collaboration to occur and reduces tension in the workplace. Thus, it is significant towards obtaining competence in communication, collaboration, and maintaining social harmony, which are essential for academic, professional, and everyday success. Supporting these findings, Salavera et al. (2017) reported that emotional intelligence is closely linked to social skills, with higher EI associated with stronger abilities to communicate, cooperate, and manage interpersonal interactions effectively. Furthermore, Khuadthong et al. (2025) demonstrated that emotional intelligence enhances communication, teamwork, and problem-solving abilities, and that integrating EI training with practical experiences can further strengthen these essential social competencies.

Self-management obtained a mean of 4.27 and SD of 0.41, interpreted as strongly agree, indicating that student training assistants possess strong self-regulatory abilities. The highest-rated item, "I set boundaries to protect my emotional well-being" with a mean of 4.68, reflects their ability to maintain professionalism and emotional control, while the lowest-rated item, "I feel lost, daydreaming in imagination" with a mean of 3.79, suggests they remain focused and composed. Overall, the high rating demonstrates their capacity to regulate emotions, adapt to challenges, and make sound decisions under pressure. Managing one's self is an important skill especially in the work place, student training assistants are expected to

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

Vol. 13, Issue 2, pp: (1-16), Month: March - April 2026, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

have this ability as it allows them to adapt and change depending on the situation they face. Supporting this, Antonopoulou (2024) explains that emotional intelligence is closely linked to self-management, as recognizing and understanding one’s emotions supports effective behavior regulation. Similarly, Shubayr and Dailah (2025) identify self-management as a core dimension of EI that reduces perceived stress and strengthens self-efficacy. Moreover, effective emotion regulation enhances coping and sustained performance in demanding situations. Overall, these findings highlight self-management as a key mechanism for emotional stability, resilience, and personal effectiveness.

Table 2 presents the level of work-life balance with the indicators: perceived work-life balance, managing work and non-work roles, work demands with personal life. The data shows a very high level of agreement with a mean of 4.31 and SD of 0.45. This suggests that the level of work life balance among student training assistants’ respondents at UM Panabo is very high.

Individuals reported high levels of work–life balance, indicating that they could effectively manage professional, personal, and academic responsibilities. Consequently, this strong balance was positively linked to greater engagement in their studies, suggesting that maintaining harmony between work and life roles can enhance active learning and commitment (De Luzuriaga-Balaria et al., 2024). Furthermore, Gragnano, Simbula, and Miglioretti (2020) examined how employees perceive different components of work–life balance, particularly the prioritization of family responsibilities versus health-related needs, and how these perceptions relate to job satisfaction. In addition, Gilla et al. (2025) found that individuals reporting very high work–life balance also demonstrated greater commitment to their profession, indicating that when educators perceive high balance, it aligns with positive educational outcomes.

Table 2. Level of Work-life balance

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Equivalent
Perceived Work-Life Balance	4.35	0.48	Strongly Agree
Managing Work and Non-Work Roles	4.34	0.50	Strongly Agree
Work Demands with Personal Life	4.24	0.46	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean	4.31	0.45	Strongly Agree

Perceived work–life balance obtained a mean score of 4.35 and SD of 0.48, with a descriptive equivalent of strongly agree, indicating that respondents perceive themselves as effectively balancing their professional responsibilities and personal lives. Among the seven questions, Item 1 achieved a high mean stating “I currently have a good balance between the time I spend at work and the time I have available for non-work activities” obtaining a mean of 4.50 and a descriptive equivalent of strongly agree. This result means that student training assistants perceive themselves as being able to juggle their work responsibilities as well as their personal life, hobbies, and activities. Oppositely, within the indicator the lowest mean is Item 2 with the statement “Overall, I believe that my work and non-work life are balanced” acquiring a mean of 4.21 and a descriptive equivalent of strongly agree. This result signifies that student training assistants have an overall high balance in their professional and personal life, able to obtain equilibrium despite their responsibilities. This very high rating suggests that they are generally capable of allocating their time and energy efficiently across multiple roles and commitments. By maintaining this balance, respondents are able to meet personal needs while remaining productive, responsible, and engaged in their work. Supporting this, Rajagopalasingam et al. (2021) revealed that strong work ethics can moderate the negative effects of competing role demands, enabling individuals to maintain a more balanced work–life experience. Moreover, Haar et al. (2017) found that employees with higher perceived work–life balance reported greater life satisfaction and better mental well-being, highlighting its positive impact beyond the workplace and its contribution to overall quality of life. Furthermore, Lofranco (2025) discovered that an individual’s perception of their work-life balance plays a critical role in influencing overall well-being, job satisfaction, and the ability to maintain consistent performance across professional and personal responsibilities.

Managing work and non-work roles obtained a high mean score of 4.34 and SD of 0.50, interpreted as strongly agree, indicating that respondents believe they can effectively balance professional and personal responsibilities. Item 7, “I prioritize my tasks to ensure both professional and family needs are met,” recorded the highest mean 4.56 with a descriptive equivalent of strongly agree, showing strong task prioritization. In contrast, Item 3, “I find it challenging to switch off from work when I am with my family and friends,” had the lowest mean of 4.15 with a descriptive equivalent of agree, suggesting minimal difficulty in transitioning between roles. Overall, the results reflect strong organizational and time-management skills, reduced role conflict, and the ability to maintain productivity and personal well-being. Work and non-work roles are two opposite sides and are a struggle to balance, student training assistants exemplify excellent balance between the two, able to manage their own time and organize within the work-place despite personal endeavor. Supporting this, Carnevale and Hatak (2020) found that flexible work practices, such as remote work, enhance employees’ capacity to manage work and family roles. Similarly, Kossek et al. (2016) emphasized that workplace flexibility and boundary control strategies improve role management by helping employees maintain clear distinctions between domains. Furthermore, Allen et al. (2020) reported that flexible arrangements and supervisor support promote better integration of work and personal responsibilities, resulting in improved work–life balance and satisfaction.

Work demands with personal life obtained a mean score of 4.24 and SD of 0.46, interpreted as strongly agree, indicating that respondents believe they can effectively manage work responsibilities while maintaining their personal lives. Within the indicator, the highest mean is Item 9 with the statement “I find it easy to disconnect from work after office hours and focus on my personal life” with a mean of 4.38 and the descriptive equivalent of "strongly agree". This result implores that student training assistants are able to detach from their work without problem, meaning they can move forward with work responsibilities but also integrate their own personal well-being and reduce the risk of overloading. Meanwhile, within the indicator the lowest mean is Item 7 stating “I have sufficient flexibility in my work hours to address urgent personal matters” This result means that despite being able to take care of personal responsibilities, student training assistants still struggle to address their own personal matters during work hours. Supporting this, Sirgy and Lee (2018) emphasize that unmanaged work demands can negatively affect overall well-being, making balance essential for maintaining quality of life and satisfaction in both work and personal domains. Similarly, French et al. (2018) found that effectively managing work and personal responsibilities is linked to higher work engagement and lower work–life conflict, reinforcing the importance of balance for employee well-being.

Presented in Table 3 is the significant relationship between emotional intelligence and work life balance among student training assistants at UM Panabo College. The independent variable, emotional intelligence, is equivalent to very high with a mean of 4.42 and SD of 0.32, while the dependent variable, work-life balance, is equivalent to very high with a mean of 4.31 and SD of 0.45.

Research consistently shows a positive relationship between emotional intelligence (EI) and work–life balance. For instance, employees in the IT sector with higher EI reported significantly better balance, as emotional regulation and self-awareness enabled them to manage competing job and personal demands more effectively (Raj, 2025). Similarly, Punitha and Karthi (2024) revealed that EI is significantly related to work–life balance and job satisfaction among employees, strengthening overall well-being and workplace outcomes. Overall, these findings indicate that stronger EI supports healthier role management and improved balance across life domains.

TABLE 3. Significant relationship between emotional intelligence and work-life balance

Variables	Mean	Description	r-value	p-value	Decision
Emotional Intelligence	4.42	Very High			
			0.708	0.000	Ho is Rejected
Work-life Balance	4.31	Very High			

R=0.708, R²=0.50

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social SciencesVol. 13, Issue 2, pp: (1-16), Month: March - April 2026, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Based on the results, emotional intelligence achieved a mean score of 4.42 while work life balance achieved a mean score of 4.31, the correlation analysis yielded an r-value of 0.708, indicating a strong positive relationship between the independent and dependent variables in this study. The p-value was 0.000, which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This demonstrates that there is a statistically significant relationship between emotional intelligence and work-life balance. Furthermore, emotional intelligence was found to account for 50.13% of the variance in work-life balance, suggesting that it plays a substantial role in influencing individuals' ability to balance professional and personal responsibilities, meanwhile other factors only account for 49.87%. The study published by Nadaraja & Harshani (2023) found that emotional intelligence has a significant positive impact on employees' work-life balance among clinical non-executive employees of a hospital, with stronger emotional intelligence associated with better balance between work and personal life. The results indicated that all dimensions of emotional intelligence were positively correlated with work-life balance, with self-management being the most influential predictor, and suggested that enhancing employees' emotional intelligence could help organizations improve their workforce's ability to manage job and life demands effectively. Moreover, Yousuf and Mir (2024) found that higher levels of emotional intelligence, particularly self-awareness and social awareness, were significantly associated with better work-life balance among higher education faculty. Moreover, a study by Abu Bakir (2018) found that managers' emotional intelligence positively impacts employees' work-life balance, demonstrating that stronger emotional competencies support better management of work and personal life responsibilities.

III. CONCLUSION

The analysis of the research results leads to the following conclusions: (1) The level of emotional intelligence of the respondents is very high with a mean 4.42 and SD of 0.32, indicating that student training assistants possess strong emotional competencies, particularly in empathy, self-awareness, self-management, self-motivation, and social skills. (2) The level of work-life balance of the respondents is also very high with a mean of 4.31 and SD of 0.45, which means that the student training assistants are generally capable of effectively managing their professional responsibilities alongside their personal lives. (3) The r-value of 0.708 and p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, signify the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates a significant and strong positive relationship between emotional intelligence and work-life balance. Furthermore, emotional intelligence was found to account for 50.13% of the variance in work-life balance, suggesting that it plays a substantial role in influencing individuals' ability to balance professional and personal responsibilities

Based on the study's findings, several recommendations are proposed. (1) Student Training Assistants (STA) should maintain their emotional intelligence at a sufficient level, and navigate through their problems with understanding of others along with balancing their work and personal needs (2) School administrations should implement programs and initiatives that sustain emotional intelligence and promote work-life balance among students. These may include self-reflection activities, stress management workshops, communication skills training, and guidance programs that support students' personal growth and academic performance (3) Teachers are encouraged to support emotional intelligence through their teaching and classroom management by addressing students' emotional needs, supporting stress management, and fostering balanced responsibilities (4) Researchers are encouraged to conduct further studies on emotional intelligence and work-life balance to expand existing knowledge, explore additional variables, and develop evidence-based strategies that can assist students' overall well-being and performance. (5) These findings can serve as a foundation for future research, allowing exploration of additional factors, development of targeted interventions, and formulation of recommendations to further complement personal and professional outcomes.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abid, S., & Barech, D. K. (2017). The impact of flexible working hours on employees' performance. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management, UK*. <https://ijecm.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/5731.pdf>
- [2] Allen, T. D., French, K. A., Dumani, S., & Shockley, K. M. (2020). A cross-national meta-analytic examination of predictors and outcomes associated with work-family conflict and work-family enrichment. *Psychological Bulletin, 146*(10), 891–929. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000230>
- [3] Antonopoulou, H. (2024). The value of emotional intelligence: Self-Awareness, Self-Regulation, motivation, and empathy as key components. *Technium Education and Humanities, 8*, 78–92. <https://doi.org/10.47577/teh.v8i.9719>

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

 Vol. 13, Issue 2, pp: (1-16), Month: March - April 2026, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [4] Arias, J., Soto-Carballo, J. G., & Pino-Juste, M. R. (2022). Emotional intelligence and academic motivation in primary school students. *Psicologia Reflexão E Crítica*, 35(1), 14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41155-022-00216-0>
- [5] Batool, B. F. (2021). Emotional intelligence and effective leadership. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(18), 1–5. <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?doi=d2be92eb4c3666495c5cee8442de6f>
- [6] Torres, J., & Brown, K. (2023). Wellness programs and social support as burnout prevention strategies. *Journal of Workplace Behavioral Health*, 38(4), 251–266. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15555240.2023.1859521>
- [7] Burmeister, E., & Aitken, L. M. (2012). Sample size: How many is enough? *Australian Critical Care*, 25(4), 271–274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aucc.2012.07.002>
- [8] Caballero-García, P. Á., & Sánchez Ruiz, S. S. (2025). Emotional Intelligence and Its Relationship with Subjective Well-Being and Academic Achievement in University Students. *Journal of Intelligence*, 13(4), Article 42. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jintelligence13040042>
- [9] Carnevale, J. B., & Hatak, I. (2020). Employee adjustment and well-being in the era of COVID-19: Implications for human resource management. *Journal of Business Research*, 116, 183–187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.05.037>
- [10] Cherry, K. (2024). Signs of low emotional intelligence. *Verywell Mind*. <https://www.verywellmind.com/signs-of-low-emotional-intelligence-279595>
- [11] Coronado-Maldonado, I., & Benítez-Márquez, M. D. (2023). Emotional intelligence, leadership, and work teams: A hybrid literature review. *Heliyon*, 9(10), e20356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e20356>
- [12] Christy, A. M., & Indiyati, H. (2025). Flexible work arrangements and employee performance: A comprehensive bibliometric study. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 14(12), 1–20.
- [13] Cuyos, I., & Permangil, J. (2025). Influence of Emotional Intelligence and Work-Life Balance on Organizational Commitment of Teachers in Public Elementary Schools in Kapalong West District. *Psychology and Education*, 43(3), 279–293. <https://doi.org/10.70838/pemj.430303>
- [14] Dangwal, A., Singhal, S., Semwal, S., & Shukla, S. (2022). Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Work-Life Balance: Evidence from IT sector. *Conference Paper, ResearchGate*.
- [15] Daribaev, A. B., & Sagindikova, N. Z. (2025). The Role of Empathy in Emotional Intelligence. *European International Journal of Pedagogics*, 5(07), 16–19. <https://doi.org/10.55640/eijp-05-07-04>
- [16] De Luzuriaga-Balaria, C. J. R., Cleofas, J. V., & Nob, R. M. (2024). Work-life balance and online student engagement among registered nurses enrolled in online graduate nursing education: A mixed methods study. *Contemporary Nurse*, 60(5), 465–478. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10376178.2024.2327350>
- [17] East Kalimantan Provincial Government. (2023). *Provinsi Kalimantan Timur Dalam Angka 2023*. Samarinda: Badan Pusat Statistik Provinsi Kalimantan Timur. <https://kaltim.bps.go.id/id/publication/2023/02/28/7a58231d5aa2f5a7b4d5c36a/pr>
- [18] Fiori, M., Bollmann, G., & Rossier, J. (2015). Exploring the path through which career adaptability increases job satisfaction and lowers job stress: The role of affect. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 91, 113–121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2015.08.010>
- [19] French, K. A., Dumani, S., Allen, T. D., & Shockley, K. M. (2018). A meta-analysis of work–family conflict and social support. *Psychological Bulletin*, 144(3), 284–314. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000120>
- [20] Gilla, K. K. C., Mag-aso, M. S., Catanio, T. D. B., Dal, J., Diagos, E. J., Antiola, J., ... Clameres, K. J. M., & Pelandas, A. M. O. (2025). Work-life balance and teaching motivation as a predictor of the commitment of public secondary school teachers. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2025.90300127>

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

 Vol. 13, Issue 2, pp: (1-16), Month: March - April 2026, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [21] Gnawali, A. (2021). Employees' Job Satisfaction and Its impact on Perceived Performance in Nepalese Public Commercial Banks. *Account and Financial Management Journal*, 04(01). <https://doi.org/10.47191/afmj/v6i1.01>
- [22] Goleman, D. (1998). *Working with emotional intelligence*. Bantam Books. <https://www.schoolofeducators.com/wp-content/uploads/2008/07/emotional-intelligence>
- [23] Gragnano, A., Simbula, S., & Miglioretti, M. (2020). Work–life balance: Weighing the importance of work–family and work–health balance. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(3), 907. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17030907>
- [24] Haar, J. M., Sune, A., Russo, M., & Ollier-Malaterre, A. (2017). Outcomes of work–life balance on job satisfaction, life satisfaction and mental health: A study across multiple cultures. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 102, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2017.06.010>
- [25] Hajibabae, F., Farahani, M. A., Ameri, Z., Salehi, T., & Hosseini, F. (2018). The relationship between empathy and emotional intelligence among Iranian nursing students. *International Journal of Medical Education*, 9, 239–243. <https://doi.org/10.5116/ijme.5b83.e2a5>
- [26] Smith, T., & Garcia, M. (2024). Impact of academic and personal balance on student well-being and success. *Journal of College Student Development*, 65(3), 221–237. <https://doi.org/10.1353/csd.2024.0021>
- [27] Hobfoll, S. E. (1989). Conservation of resources: A new attempt at conceptualizing stress. *American Psychologist*, 44(3), 513–524. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066x.44.3.513>
- [28] Hyman, J. (2005). Work-life balance: Employee and employer perspectives. *Journal of Human Resource Management*, 15(4), 411–427. <https://www.scribd.com/document/666188744/Work-life-Balance-Hyman-2005>
- [29] Khuadthong, B., Pantaruk, S., Imjai, N., & Aujirapongpan, S. (2025). Bridging theory and practice: The roles of emotional intelligence and work-integrated learning in developing social skills of tourism and hospitality Gen Z students. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 12, 102194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2025.102194>
- [30] Kossek, E. E., Valcour, M., & Lirio, P. (2016). The sustainable workforce: Organizational strategies for promoting work–life balance and well-being. *Organizational Dynamics*, 45(3), 258–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orgdyn.2016.07.003>
- [31] Lofranco, M. C. (2025). The interwoven effects of organizational culture, work-life balance, and instructional leadership on school administrators' work performance: A structural equation modeling approach. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Marvin-Lofranco/publication/396702930>
- [32] Malik, M. (2021). Health related quality of life perceived among caregivers and breast cancer patients in Pakistan: Time to ponder. *American Journal of Biomedical Science & Research*, 11(5), 370–376. <https://doi.org/10.34297/ajbsr.2021.11.001663>
- [33] Martin, J., & Thomas, K. (2024). The influence of emotional intelligence on classroom behavior and student engagement. *Educational Psychology*, 44(2), 230–246. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2023.1903854>
- [34] Martizano, L. K., & Baloran, E. (2025). Emotional Intelligence and Work-Life Balance as determinants of individual work performance of public elementary school teachers. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5165863>
- [35] Mayer, J. D., Salovey, P., & Caruso, D. R. (2020). Emotional intelligence: New ability or eclectic traits? *American Psychologist*, 75(4), 452–466. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000694>
- [36] Memon, S., Asif, S., & Hussain, S. (2021). Emotional intelligence and work-life balance: A study of working women teachers in public sector universities. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 9(2), 141–149. <https://mgesjournals.com/hssr/article/view/hssr.2021.9214>

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social SciencesVol. 13, Issue 2, pp: (1-16), Month: March - April 2026, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [37] Nadaraja, R., & Harshani, M. D. R. (2023). Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Employee Work-Life Balance: A Study of Clinical, Non-Executive Level Employees in ABC Hospital (Pvt) Ltd. *Kelaniya Journal of Human Resource Management*. <https://doi.org/10.4038/kjhrm.v18i2.122>
- [38] Nanda, M., & Randhawa, G. (2020). Emotional intelligence, work-life balance, and work-related well-being: A proposed mediation model. *Colombo Business Journal*, *11*(2). <https://doi.org/10.4038/cbj.v11i2.62>
- [39] Naz, S., Ahmad, S., & Batoool, A. (2021). Emotional intelligence and work-life balance: A study of working women teachers in public sector universities. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, *9*(2), 141–149. <https://doi.org/10.18510/hssr.2021.9214>
- [40] Brown, L., & Nguyen, A. (2024). Mindfulness and stress management in the workplace: Effects on work-life balance. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, *29*(1), 56–68. <https://doi.org/10.1037/ocp0000300>
- [41] Nieto-Carracedo, A., Gómez-Iñiguez, C., Tamayo, L. A., & Igartua, J.-J. (2024). Emotional intelligence and academic achievement relationship: Emotional well-being, motivation, and learning strategies as mediating factors. *Psicología Educativa*, *30*(2), 67–74. <https://doi.org/10.5093/psed2024a7>
- [42] Pathak, K. (2021). Work Life balance major key driver for Employee Engagement. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, *12*(6), 4971–4978. <https://turcomat.org/index.php/turkbilmate/article/view/8745>
- [43] Prabha, S., Tritiyaan, N., Dua, B. (2023). The role of Emotional Intelligence in Interpersonal Relationship and Success. *Shodha Prabha*, *112*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/384610212>
- [44] Yuliani, N. L., & Sutrisno, W. (2025). The impact of workload and flexible work hours on employee engagement. *Journal of Management and Sustainability*, *15*(1), 45–58. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jms.v15n1p45>
- [45] Punitha, N., & Karthi, G. (2024). Work–Life Balance, Job Satisfaction, Job Performance: The Mediating Role of Emotional Intelligence. *Journal of Digital Economy*. <https://journalofdigitaleconomy.org/index.php/JDE/article/view/93>
- [46] Raj, Y. (2025). Association Between Emotional Intelligence and Work-Life Balance Among Indian IT Employees: A Quantitative Study. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.25215/1303.110>
- [47] Rajagopalasingam, V., Fernando, R. L. S., & Ramanayake, U. B. (2021). Impacts of Perceived Role Demands on Work-Life Balance and Moderating Effects of Work Ethics: Evidence from Public Sector Professionals in Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Business and Management*, *15*(8), 115. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v15n8p115>
- [48] Ravalier, P., Wegrzynek, S., & Lawton, S. (2016). Systematic review: complementary therapies and employee well-being. *Occupational Medicine*, *66*(6), 428–436. <https://doi.org/10.1093/occmed/kqw047>
- [49] Saleem, R., Ullah, N., & Zafar, J. M. (2024). Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Students' Academic Performance at University Level: A Novel Perspective. *Pakistan Social Sciences Review*, *8*(4), 586–595. [https://doi.org/10.35484/pssr.2024\(8-IV\)54](https://doi.org/10.35484/pssr.2024(8-IV)54)
- [50] Sánchez Ruiz, S. S., & Caballero-García, P. Á. (2025). Emotional Intelligence and Its Relationship with Subjective Well-Being and Academic Achievement in University Students. *Journal of Intelligence*, *13*(4), Article 42. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jintelligence13040042>
- [51] Schutte, N. S., Malouff, J. M., & Bhullar, N. (2021). The impact of emotional intelligence on health and well-being: A meta-analytic review. *Personality and Individual Differences*, *168*, 110348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2020.110348>
- [52] Sembiring, A. A. R. B., Hardjo, S., & Lubis, R. (2024). Role of Emotional Intelligence Towards Work-Life Balance with Support Family as Mediator Variables. *Bulletin of Counseling and Psychotherapy*, *6*(1). <https://doi.org/10.51214/00202406840000>

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

 Vol. 13, Issue 2, pp: (1-16), Month: March - April 2026, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [53] Sharma, S., & Saxena, P. (2022). Impact of job stress and emotional intelligence on work–life balance: A study among Indian nurses. *International Journal of Behavioural and Healthcare Research*. <https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/10.1504/IJBHR.2022.127110>
- [54] Shengyao, Y., Xuefen, L., Jenatabadi, H. S., Samsudin, N., Chunchun, K., & Ishak, Z. (2024). Emotional intelligence impact on academic achievement and psychological well-being among university students: The mediating role of positive psychological characteristics. *BMC Psychology*, 12, Article 389. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-024-01886-4>
- [55] Shylaja, P., & Prasad, C. (2017). Emotional intelligence and work life balance. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 19(05), 18–21. <https://doi.org/10.9790/487x-1905051821>
- [56] Sirgy, M. J., & Lee, D. J. (2018). Work-life balance: An integrative review. *Applied Research in Quality of Life*, 13(1), 229–254. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11482-017-9509-8>
- [57] Staff, C. (2025). Work-Life Balance: What it is and 5 Ways to Improve Yours. *Coursera*. <https://www.coursera.org/articles/work-life-balance>
- [58] Syahada, L. E., & Suhardi, R. F. (2025). The effect of work-life balance, work stress, and workload on employee performance with organizational support as moderator. *Daengku Journal*, 5(2), 264–276. <https://jurnal.ahmar.id/index.php/daengku/article/view/3813>
- [59] Hemosilla, J., & Tan, J. B. (2023). Emotional intelligence and Work-Life balance of employees in a state college. *Ejournals.ph*. <https://www.ejournals.ph/article.php?id=20683>
- [60] Velasco, A. M., & Apostol, S. V. (2024). Stress, emotional intelligence, and work-life balance among public elementary school teachers in Cateel, Davao Oriental. *Philippine Educational Journal*, 48(2), 134–152.
- [61] Vestal, A. (2020). The relationship between nurses’ emotional intelligence and their perceived work performance. *Core.ac.uk*, 3(9(1)), 115–124. <https://core.ac.uk/reader/230830560>
- [62] Vestal, A. (2015). The relationship between nurses’ emotional intelligence and their perceived work performance. *Core.ac.uk*. <https://core.ac.uk/reader/230830560>
- [63] Lee, A., & Martinez, R. (2025). The role of institutional support in reducing student anxiety and improving academic focus. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 48(2), 115–130. <https://erquarterly.org/vol48no2/lee-martinez>
- [64] Zhou, Z., Tavan, H., Kavarizadeh, F., Sarokhani, M., & Sayehmiri, K. (2024). The relationship between emotional intelligence, spiritual intelligence, and student achievement: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Medical Education*, 24, Article 217. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-024-05208-5>